

comparing its spectral characteristics with those of authentic sample, reported in lit.⁸

Experimental

B. ps. are uncorrected. IR spectra (thin films) were recorded on a Perkin Elmer infrared spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded at 60 MHz using TMS as an internal reference in CCl_4 as solvent.

Ethyl 7, 11-dimethyl-3-oxo-6, 10-dodecadienoate (II). This was obtained exactly according to the procedure laid down in lit.⁹

Ethyl 7, 11-dimethyl-3-chloro-2, 6, 10-dodecatrienoate (III). The compound (II, 7.9 g) was added dropwise with stirring to the solution of PCl_5 (2.8 g) in dry chloroform (40 ml.). The stirring was continued for 4 hr. and it was left overnight. The contents were decomposed with cold water, the organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was dried and the solvent was expelled under reduced pressure furnishing the chloride (III, 5.45 g) in 65% yield; ν_{max} 1710, 1620, 1460, 1310, 1233, 1170, 1140, 1120, and 767 cm^{-1} , (Found: C, 67.61; H, 8.72%; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_2$ Cl. requires C, 67.55; H, 8.80%;)

Ethyl 3, 7, 10-trimethyl-2E, 6, 10-dodecatrienoate (IV). To the solution of the reagent in ether, prepared from the reaction of methyl-lithium (237 ml., 1.34N) in ether with cuprous iodide (26.6 g) molar ratio 2 : 1, at 0° under nitrogen atmosphere, was added slowly the compound (III, 9 g). The stirring was continued for 4 hr. and it was left overnight. The contents were decomposed with cold water and product was extracted with ether and ether extract was dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue after solvent evaporation was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina using pet. ether : benzene (4 : 1) as eluent, providing (IV, 4.55g) in 55% yield; ν_{max} 1715, 1115, 1020 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$). (Found: C, 77.10; H, 10.58. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.22; H, 10.67%).

3,7,10-Trimethyl-2E, 6, 10-dodecatrienol (I). To a fine suspension of LAH (420 mg) in benzene (50 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of ester (IV, 2.4 g) in benzene (20 ml.) maintaining the temp. at 60°. The contents were further stirred for 8 hr at 60°. After usual work up and distillation under reduced pressure it afforded (I, 1.3 g.) in 60% yield; ν_{max} 3450, 1630, 1395, 1350, 1110, 1015, 970, 840 and 810 cm^{-1} . NMR (60MHz CCl_4) spectrum showed signals at τ : 8.3–8.42 (9H,m, allylic methyl), 7.92–8.1 (1H,m, allylic methylene and $-\text{CH}_3$ at C_2), 5.9 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) and 4.6–5.0 (3H,m, vinylic protons). (Found: C, 84.71; H, 7.55. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.87; H, 7.60%).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (SDK) is thankful to C.S.I.R. for awarding a junior research fellowship to him.

Thanks are also due to Dr. Sujan Singh, Banaras Hindu University for recording the NMR spectra given in this paper.

References

1. L. WEILER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 6702.
2. S. N. HUCKIN and L. WEILER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 1082.
3. O. P. VIG, A. K. VIG and S. D. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974 (Communicated).
4. O. P. VIG, A. K. VIG and S. D. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974 (Communicated).
5. F. ELZE *Chem. Ztg.*, 1910, **34**, 810; 1913, **37**, 1422; H. SODEN and W. TREFF, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 1094.
6. M. KERSCHBAUM, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 1732.
7. G. POPJAB, J. W. CORNFORTH, R. H. CORNFORTH, R. RYHAGE and D. GOODMANN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1962, **237**, 56.
8. L. RUZICKA, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1923, **6**, 492.
9. O. P. VIG, J. C. KAPUR, C. K. KHANNA and B. VIG., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 505.
10. E. J. COREY and G. H. POSNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 3911.
11. C. P. CASEY and D. F. MARTEN, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1974, 925.
12. E. I. SNYDER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **32**, 3531.

Constituents of the Roots of *Selinum papyraceum*

BISHAN D. GUPTA, SUNIL K. BANERJEE *
and K. L. HANDA

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu-Tawi

Manuscript received 19 May 1975; accepted 27 April 1976

ONLY three species of *Selinum* (Umbelliferae), *S. vaginatum*^{1,2}, *S. tenuifolium*³, and *S. monnieri*⁴ have been chemically investigated so far for coumarins. In view of this it was thought desirable to undertake a chemical investigation on another *Selinum* species, viz. *S. papyraceum* C. B. Clarke.

Dried and powdered roots of *S. papyraceum* (collected from the Eastern Himalayas) were extracted with petrol (b. p. 60°-80°) for 20 hr. The extract showed at least six u. v. fluorescent spots on TLC. The residue from the petrol extract was chromatographed on silica gel. No crystalline product could be isolated from petrol and petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluates,

Fractions from benzene eluates were combined (on the basis of TLC pattern) and rechromatographed on silica gel. Solvent was removed from the first fractions and the residue crystallised from methanol to give sitosterol, m.p. 137° (positive Lieberman-Burchard test, Co, TLC, m.m.p., acetate, m.p. 129°).

Further elution with benzene gave fractions showing three spots on TLC. Preparative TLC on silica gel G using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as the solvent afforded a product in small yields. It melted at 116°-117° and showed pale brown u. v. fluorescence. IR and NMR data revealed the identity of the product with knidilin (I)⁵.

In the IR, it absorbs at $\nu_{\max}$ 1722, 1592, 821 cm^{-1} (coumarin). The NMR spectrum was taken in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as the internal reference. It showed peaks at δ (in p.p.m) 1.66, 1.74 (C-methyls), 4.18 (s, methoxy), 4.80 (d, $J=7$ Hz, α -methylene), 5.42 (t, $J=7$ Hz, vinyl), 6.28 (d, $J=10$ Hz, H-3), 6.98 (d, $J=2$ Hz, H-3'), 7.67 (d, $J=2$ Hz, H-2') and 8.15 ($J=10$ Hz, H-4). This is the second report on the occurrence of knidilin in nature. Elution with benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) afforded xanthotoxin, m.p. 144° (yellow fluorescence in u.v, m.m.p., Co-TLC, IR and NMR).

The benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluate yielded a residue which on crystallization from petrol-ethyl acetate gave isopimpinellin, m.p. 148°-149°, pale yellow needles (brown fluorescence in u. v., m.m.p., Co-TLC, IR and NMR).

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. C. K. Atal, Director of this institute for encouragement. Sincere thanks are also due to Dr. B. C. Subba Rao of Hindustan Lever Ltd., Bombay for the IR, and NMR spectra.

References

1. K. RAJENDRAN, C. K. MESTA, S. K. PAKNIKAR and S. C. BHATTACHARYYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 200.
2. T. R. SESHADRI and VISHWAPPAUL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 418.
3. N. ADITYACHAUDHURY and D. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 1067.
4. B. E. NIELSEN, 'The Biology and Chemistry of the Umbelliferae' (Ed). V. H. Heywood, Academic Press, London, 1971, p. 325.
5. N. F. KOMISSARENKO and V. T. CHERNOBAI, *Khim. Prir. Soedin.*, 1966, p. 375.

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Halogeno-Chalcones and Flavones

Y. B. VIBHUTE

Department of Chemistry, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya,
Nanded (431 602), Maharashtra

Manuscript received 21 January 1976 ; revised 30 April 1976 ;
accepted 6 May 1976

A number of chalcones and flavones have been shown active against various bacterial infections. Misra¹⁻³ have reported the germicidal activity of naphthyl and phenanthryl chalcones. Sharma et al.⁴

has reported the bactericidal activity of some flavones. Therefore an attempt was made to study the antimicrobial activity of some chalcones and flavones, synthesised by halogenation of 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone.

On keeping resacetophenone and α -naphthaldehyde in the presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide for 16 hr. and then on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave a yellow product, which gave violet red coloration with ferric chloride and yellow coloration to Wilson test⁵. Yellow product on methylation and acetylation gave dimethoxy and diacetyl chalcone respectively. Further infrared spectra of compound showed a band at 1625 cm^{-1} due to carbonyl group and band at 1540 cm^{-1} due to carbon carbon double bond. Therefore 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone structure was assigned to it.

2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone on iodination with one mole of iodine and iodic acid, gave monoiododerivative methyl ether of which on ethanolic potassium hydroxide hydrolysis gave the known α -naphthoic acid⁶. The monoiododerivative was also obtained by condensing 5-iodoresacetophenone⁷, with α -naphthaldehyde in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide. Therefore 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-5'-iodo-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone structure was assigned to the above monoiododerivative. With two, three or with eight moles of iodinating agent, it gave a di-iododerivative. Methylene ether of which on hydrolysis with ethanolic potassium hydroxide hydrolysis gave a known α -naphthoic acid⁶. The di-iododerivative was also obtained by condensing 3,5-di-iodoresacetophenone⁷, with α -naphthaldehyde in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide. 2',4'-dihydroxy-3',5'-di-iodophenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone structure was therefore assigned to the above di-iododerivative.

With one or two moles of bromine in acetic acid, 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone did not give any pure product but with excess of bromine in acetic acid (eight moles), yielded a tetrabromoderivative. Methylene ether of which on ethanolic alkaline hydrolysis gave a known 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxy salicylic acid⁸. Tetrabromoderivative on heating with acetic acid and potassium acetate yielded dibromoflavone. Methyl ether of which on ethanolic alkaline hydrolysis gave a known 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxy salicylic acid⁸. Therefore, 6,8-dibromo-7-hydroxy-2-(α -naphthyl) chromone structure was assigned to above dibromoflavone and 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-3',5'- α - β -tetrabromo- β -1-naphthylethyl ketone to tetrabromoderivative.

The purity of all the compounds was checked by T.L.C.

All above chalcones gave yellow coloration to Wilson test⁶.

The infrared absorption spectra of these compounds (Table 2) in Nujol mulls showed the conjugated carbon carbon double bond band at 1600-1540 cm^{-1} (1-7-and